

Effect of Covid-19 on Sikkim tourism – a Case Study

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to publicise the impact of the life-threatening corona virus disease on tourism sector in a small state of India, called Sikkim. The pandemic has caused a lot of flutter and has led to fall in world's economies. Tourism has always been a major contributor to any country's economy and like any fluctuations, this industry gets hit predominantly thereby shaking the livelihood of the people involved. Pandemics have always played a major role in disrupting the economies and CoViD-19 is no different. At the onset of this pandemic, this research projects the importance of tourism in Indian economy, the role of migrant workers and the causal effect on their livelihood because of the pandemic. The focus of the research is the impact on tourism in Sikkim, where no CoViD-19 cases were reported till 22nd May 2020. The research highlights the problems faced by various stakeholders in the tourism industry and the impact it has on the locals. Remedial measures have also been suggested to promote and revive healthy tourism with all safety measures.

Keywords: Sikkim, Tourism, CoViD-19, Economy.

1. Introduction

One of the fastest growing industries in the world is tourism. So, what is tourism industry and who are the stakeholders and participants in this industry? According to the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), tourism industry refers to “all establishments for which the principal activity is a tourism characteristic activity”.

This ever-booming industry includes hotels, catering, restaurants, travel agencies, tourist guides, tourist information offices, conference and exhibitions, cultural sites, casinos etc. It is a known fact that the hospitality sector contributes a lion's share of approximately 50-75% of all jobs in the industry. Tourism on the global platform employs close to one tenth of the global workers.

However, the wages in this industry are often too low paid and are considered as low status which are seasonal and temporary in nature. Certain remote tourism involves life risk and can be promoted only by the locals who understand the topography of the area. The growth in the economy because of tourism has put pressure on the industry to recruit migrant workers. The demand for workers increases as development progresses. "The continuing growth in the demand for labour, particularly with certain specialized skills, is likely to outstrip local sources, which creates the need for labour migration".

At first, the migration is likely to happen from rural to urban areas, or to tourist hotspots, to fill the skill gaps. As the development progresses, people are likely to move across borders to find means for their livelihood.

At the onset of the tourism boom, China reported the pandemic towards the end of December 2019, creating havoc and panic in all sectors. The initial outbreak spread like a wildfire across nations, spreading exponentially, infecting close to 4.4 million people across the world. Governments have responded by closing their borders, imposing bans on entrants, and closing all the state borders.

Public spaces were forced to shut to enforce social distancing. Transport facilities were reduced, and a complete lockdown was enforced throughout the country.

2. Sikkim and the impact of CoViD-19

Sikkim, a north eastern state in India, is the second smallest and the least populated state in India. It borders China in the north, Bhutan in the east, Nepal in the west and the Indian state of West Bengal in the south. Sikkim boasts of being a fully organic state with regard to agriculture and is deemed to be India’s most “environmentally conscious” state. The gross domestic product (GDP) of Sikkim is dependent mainly on terrace farming of rice and cultivation of cash crops. Despite having minimal industrial infrastructure, the state’s economy has been one among the fastest growing economy. According to the Indian states GDP database, the state’s GDP expanded by 89.93% in 2010 alone. Furthermore, in recent years, the government of Sikkim has prioritized tourism as a contributor to its economy, because of which the revenue has increased 14 times since mid-90s. The state has also invested in a full-fledged gambling industry which promotes both casinos and online gambling. The opening of the Nathu La pass has been billed as a boon for Sikkim’s economy.

This table shows annual growth in each state's nominal GSDP growth in percentage

Table 1. Nominal GSDP growth in India and Sikkim

State/Union territory	2010 –11	2011 –12	2012 –13	2013 –14	2014 –15	2015 –16	2016 –17	2017 –18
India	18.66	15.77	13.80	13.0	11.0	10.4	10.8	10.0
Sikkim	20.85	16.24	10.5	12.30	11.10	17.10	11.00	11.10

Source: "[Gross State Domestic Product \(GSDP\) at Current Prices \(as on 31-05-2014\)](#)" (PDF). Planning Commission Government of India. Archived from [the original](#) (PDF) on 15 July 2014.

The following table shows the annual growth in nominal GSDP for the financial years 2011–12 to 2020–21, from the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation.

Table 2. Nominal GSDP from 2011–12 to 2018–2019

State/Union territory	2011–12 in ₹ Cr ore	2012–13 in ₹ Cr ore	2013–14 in ₹ Cror e	2014–15 in ₹ Cror e	2015–16 in ₹ Cror e	2016–17 in ₹ Cror e	2017–18 in ₹ Cror e	2018–19 in ₹ Cro re
India	87,36,039	99,46,636	1,12,36,635	1,24,33,749	1,36,75,331	1,52,51,028	1,70,95,005	1,90,10,16
Sikkim	11,165	12,338	13,862	15,407	18,034	20,687	23,495	26,786

Source: "MOSPI Gross State Domestic Product". *Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India*. 1 August 2019. Retrieved 16 September 2019.

Tourism in Sikkim is as important as air or water. It is the largest employment generating sector for the whole state. Reports suggest that 7 out of every 10 families are connected to tourism that generates a business of around 2000 crores in a year. At least 40% of premium class foreign tourists visiting Nepal or Bhutan prefer touching Sikkim. Arrival of close to 1.5 lakhs foreign tourists and around 14 lakhs domestic visitors in a year contributes a significant share in the annual tourism business. In 2019, more than 1.2 million Indian tourists visited Sikkim and the number of foreigners visiting Sikkim stood at 133,388. Among the foreigners, Bangladeshis accounted for 60,542 visitors followed by Nepal with 56,781 visitors.

The others came from USA (2250), Germany (1674), UK (1412), Australia (1129), France (1121), Thailand (899), Malaysia (744) and Canada (568).

3. CoViD-19 effect:

Generally, whenever there has been any major impact on the economy, tourism has always been the first one to get affected as people start to cut down on their travel budgets. In case of CoViD-19, the tourism sector has a direct role to play since most cases have been recorded in places with high number of tourists and migrants.

As per reports, millions of jobs in the global tourism industry has been lost due to ongoing pandemic. So, how has the pandemic affected one of the cleanest and the remotest state in India is the big question. The answer is, despite zero CoViD confirm patient till 22nd May, 2020, its tourism sector is badly hit.

The government's plan to ban tourism till October 2020 threatens livelihood of thousands of people in the state.

Economic revival committee has also been set in state by government which has started working on restoring the state's economy by reviewing measures to improve tourism and hospitality. Sector wise analysis of targets are underway which will promote recovery from the loss due to CoViD-19 pandemic.

Problems faced:

Here is a brief case study of how the pandemic has affected the stake holders in Sikkim.

1. A cab driver in Gangtok, who is the sole bread winner in his family is quite worried about repaying the car loan. He bought the vehicle on instalment two years back to earn his living. With the curb on tourism till October, he will not be able to pay the monthly instalments of the car loan, which will leave him jobless. There are many such people who ply cabs in Sikkim for their livelihood and are likely to lose their jobs.

2. Non-Sikkimese: Most of the tourism businesses in Sikkim are run by non-locals in partnership with the locals. Many hotels are leased out to Non-Sikkimese businessmen who are facing massive losses with the stagnant tourism sector.

Lockdown has pushed hotel business in the travel industry hotspot Sikkim to the edge where speculators from Bengal and different states are the main tire casualties. Equivalent victim is over 70% of Sikkim's populace reliant on hospitality industry that creates around Rs.1.5k business there in a year.

Settled in nature's lap, Sikkim has around 15 lakhs residential and 1.5 lakh remote visitors every year in its close to 2000 lodgings and hotels with aggregate around 35,000 rooms. This acquires a business volume of around 650 crores from housing in particular. Counting food, transportation, and all different ancillaries the all-out accommodation business volume of the state comes around 1.5 k crore. "Over 80% of these inns are run on rent. The rent sum for rent holder is determined relying on limit, quality, or area of the property. The robust rent sum running Rs 1.5 lakh to 2.5 lakhs for every room every year should be paid ahead of time or in portions," said the Director of a Hotel organization that runs numerous properties in Sikkim on rent.

As the general pattern goes, Sikkim inns get around 90 to 100 days over 90% inhabitation. April, May, June, the pinnacle season, contributes 60 days in it. In the end, rent holders settle conventions by paying the sum before beginning of summer, as per the General Secretary of Himalayan Hospitality and Tourism Development Network (HHTDN).

Sikkim Govt has prevented passage of anybody from outside following beginning of the pandemic. When it is finished, it will be practically blustery season, the most

vulnerable season for slopes. The state couldn't begin summer business this time, which is the opinion of the tourism advisor to Govt. of Sikkim.

Leaseholders are generally from Bengal and barely any different states. Following zero return now, it has gotten too hard to even consider meeting up our liabilities. On the opposite side, proprietors getting lease instalment on a monthly basis will undoubtedly miss next portions and face inconvenience.

As per a study, the gross value addition contributed by the tourism sector to the state's GDP was 7.89% in the financial year 2013-2014 and the number of people directly employed were 43,870, which is approximately 7.19% of the state's total population. The stakeholders and people in this sector namely guide, hotel operators, local people are majorly hit since their source of income is through tourism.

3. Also, most of the tourism business is run by the non-locals, the natives are unwilling to work in their own state and have moved to other places for employment. With the pandemic hitting worldwide, Sikkimese working in Nepal and other neighbouring states are forced to walk to reach their hometown with little money given by their owners.
4. Since Sikkim turned into a 100 percent natural express, the inflow of voyagers has expanded by 25 percent and had promoted wellness tourism industry. The pandemic leading to closure of the state borders has also indirectly affected the farmers. As per the reports by the Guardian, Organic farmers have sold their produce to the tourists which the local people are unwilling to buy. The organic vegetables and fruits are more expensive and hence not enough locals visit the organic market. (theguardian.com/global-development, authored by Vidhi Doshi, 31 Jan 2017)
5. Further, the artisans and artists promoting Sikkim culture have also been affected, with their livelihood at stake.

6. The dip in tourism is mainly due to the ban on entry of foreigners announced by Sikkim and by Bhutan after an American tourist travelling from India was tested positive for the deadly disease after his arrival at Paro, about 50km from capital Thimphu.
7. The government will not issue Inner Line Permit (ILP) to foreigners, including Bhutan nationals.
8. It additionally reported a sweeping boycott to visits to Nathula pass on the Indo-China outskirts. "Following the declarations, in excess of 1500 vacationers who were coming back from Phuentsholing, the border town in Bhutan, are confronting trouble," said Suresh Thakuri, leader of Jaigaon Travel Welfare Association. The Kailash Mansarovar Yatra and border trade between India and China through the Nathula pass will not take place this year due to the coronavirus outbreak, Sikkim Tourism Minister B S Panth said.
9. The border goods exchange through Nathula Pass was booked to start in May while the Kailash Mansarovar Yatra through the course was scheduled to initiate in June. The Ministry of External Affairs sorts out the yatra from June-September every year through two unique courses - Lipulekh Pass (Uttarakhand) and Nathu La Pass (Sikkim). Kailash Mansoravar is in Tibet. The Nathula border trade between India and China resumed in 2006 after a gap of more than four decades while the annual Kailash Mansarovar Yatra through the pass had begun two years ago.

As per the sources, "Sikkim's travel industry segment has been seriously hit due to the coronavirus episode, with the state government missing out income of more than Rs 10 crore".

The loss of income is because of the restriction on passage of residential and remote sightseers to the state since the primary seven day stretch of March taking into account the coronavirus flare-up.

4. Remedial measures:

1. The tourism stakeholders should be given a waiver of SGST and Municipal taxes for hotels.
2. Moratorium on payment of loans to be extended for hotels, travel agencies and tourist vehicle owners.
3. Government to provide relief on the “lease value” for hotels, which can balance the demands of both owners and lease holders.
4. Unemployment being one of the major concerns, specifically for locals who do not prefer working in Sikkim due to major outsourcing by the private players, government should strictly impose initiatives like “atmanirbhar” or self-sustenance in Sikkim. Locals should be educated and trained to stay in their hometown and promote Sikkim tourism from their perspective.
5. Tourists entering the state by road or airways should be checked for temperature and their blood samples should be tested for any recent intake of paracetamols or other fever reducing medications.
6. Encouraging eco-tourism to enable sustainable living while they travel- which includes promoting local food and snacks, usage of steel sipper bottles.
7. Encouraging research on low cost organic farming techniques which in turn reduces the cost of organic vegetables leading to the locals buying the organic produce.
8. Enhance and promote local festivals and culture thereby providing work for artisans and artists to sustain their livelihood.

9. Promote local cuisine and savouries, which in turn promotes employment for both men and women and see active participation in hosting the tourists.
10. Arogya app initiated by Government of India should be made mandatory for all the guests which helps feasible Guest tracking system.
11. Online payment systems should be made robust throughout the state, which eventually avoids any contact or spread of virus through cash transfers.
12. Visitors should carry valid medical certificate from Government recognised CoViD-19 Doctors stating that the visitors are fit to travel and are no asymptotic carriers of any kind of virus.
13. Travellers may prefer less crowded destinations that maintain extreme hygiene with compulsory sanitizing and masking and social distancing norms. All tourist places to follow the norms of social distancing with extreme level of hygiene.
14. Transport: share taxis shall have limited number of people. Allow self-driving sanitized rental car facilities with a local guide can enhance the tourist experience. Travellers may also prefer digitized travel option as of now.
15. Promotional activities on yoga, wellness, wildlife, cuisine and culture of Sikkim could attract the future tourist for all the 4 districts. Improving infrastructure near the hotels with regard to safety and hygiene will be an added advantage to promote safe tourism.
16. Conduct frequent meetings with locals and tourism players and chalk out plans about hygiene and usage of PPEs for a contactless experience.
17. Reusable masks to be used at all places, with proper measures to be taken to dispose used PPEs, masks and sanitiser bottles there by creating an awareness to use only eco-friendly goods.
18. Increase more awareness about taking preventive measures for CoViD-19 in tourist areas through advertising in boards, tv adds, social media, mobiles, hotels.

19. Hotels should have a doctor on call facility to attend to emergency.
20. Encourage local entrepreneurs. Hotels can offer tourists for using local soaps, local napkin/sanitizer, local masks, offer local wine / drinks and Sikkim liquors.
21. Employ more local culture groups to show cultural dance to tourists at hotels.
22. Other kinds of taxes on power, garbage, water should be relaxed for at least one year.
23. Non-Sikkimese should be strictly checked with regard to running business and being a major stakeholder in the Sikkim tourism industry. Locals should be given priority and 85% share must be held by the locals to boost the industry which in turn favours the economy of the state.
24. Children should be taught about wellness and hygiene right from their elementary classes and Sikkim culture should be taught as part of their regular curriculum.
25. Infrastructure development in terms of transport and other facilities should be given priority and measures should be taken to enhance the infrastructure without disturbing the ecosystem of the state.

5. Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic has created a huge loss to economy in general and has impacted the tourism industry to a larger extent. The restrictions on travel has created a slump in demand among the nationwide travellers. Foreign arrivals in March 2020 fell by 66.4% year-on-year. Sikkim, with zero confirmed positive case till 22nd May, 2020, has managed to restrict the spread of the virus, but with a major loss to the livelihood of the locals. The tourism sector can be revived by enabling more testing centres in the state and with stringent measures on hygiene and safety. Furthermore, the locals should be enlightened with the noble cause of self-sustainability and trained to understand the importance of their own resources. Tourism can also be boosted with the use of local foods and culture, and by giving moratorium to the affected lot.

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